

The Influence of Ancient Bharatiya Sanskriti on Western Women: A Journey of Spiritual and Cultural Transformation

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Abstract

Ancient Bharatiya Sanskriti, rooted in spiritual wisdom, has profoundly influenced Western women, offering a transformative alternative to materialistic and patriarchal cultures. This paper explores the appeal of Indian spirituality, particularly the veneration of the feminine divine, which empowers and inspires Western women. Key concepts such as Shakti, Sanskriti, and the holistic practices of yoga, meditation, and Ayurveda resonate deeply, fostering inner peace and balance. While embracing Indian philosophy and lifestyle, Western women undergo personal transformation, integrating simplicity, non-violence, and spirituality into their lives. However, challenges like cultural appropriation and misinterpretation persist. This cross-cultural engagement promotes global spirituality and reclaims the authenticity of India's ancient traditions, offering a meaningful path for those seeking deeper spiritual fulfillment and personal growth.

Keywords Sanskriti, Western Women, Culture.

Introduction

The sacred land of Bhartavarsha is the land of sages, seers, rishis and Munis. The land, where the True Lord Himself incarnated in various forms. Bharata is the land of Knowledge, which enlightens the whole world irrespective of their caste, class and ideological differences. Although the idea of nationalism and liberty was developed in France, Spain, Germany, Italy and England but this idea of nation puts limitation on imparting knowledge to the world. The idea of nationalism is an ideology, but our tradition teaches *Rashtra-Bhakti*, the selfless devotion. If we consider *Rashtra-Bhakti* as patriotism then we will be unable to understand Bharata where people believe that all elements are made up of five elements (*Pancha-Tattva*): air, earth, fire, sky, and water. Our body is also made up of these five *tattva*, so that's why our body is attached to this world, the earth, the land where we live. As it is mentioned in Rig Veda 1.1.1:

ॐ अग्निमीळे पुरोहितं यज्ञस्य देवमृत्विजम् । होतारं रत्नधातमम् ॥१॥

Om, I praise Agni who is the Purohita (Priest) of the Yagya (Sacrifice) (Priest leading the Sacrifice), (as well as) its Ritvij (Priest performing Sacrifice at proper times); the Yagya which is directed towards the Devas.

Here the priest is worshipping Agni which is not *Vibhakta* (detached) from him. Agni was worshipped in the form of *Chetana* (consciousness), and Chetana is eternal and can never be ended. The land where Agni always lightens is known as Bharata, even Agni is also known as Bharata.[1] Even nowadays, many women in the villages of Bharata never blow the Agni (fire) as it is dedicated to consciousness. We become conscious (from sleep) when the sun rises and sun is the ultimate source of energy that's why Surya (Sun) is called as Bharat, and the land of the lineage of sun (suryavanshis) is known as Bharatavarsha.

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to study the influence of ancient Bharatiya Sanskriti on western women.

Review of Literature

Although the land of Bharata is not as it was in ancient times. As it was written by Dr. B.R Ambedkar in his book "Pakistan or The Partition of India": "Unity of ancient India is definitely a historical truth... Chinese traveler Hiuen Tsang when visited India in the 7th AD recorded, what is now Afghanistan, was also part of India... but what has happened since Hiuen Tsang left India? The most important thing that has happened is the invasion of India by the Muslim hordes from the north-west. The first consequence of these invasion was the breaking up of the unity of North India with the rest of India... the whole of north India would have served from India, had it not been for the check provided by the rise of Sikhs. The methods adopted by the invaders had left behind its aftermath. One aftermath is the bitterness between the Hindus and Muslim. The national unity must be founded on the sense of kinship in the feeling of being kindred. In short it must be spiritual. The remnants of binding cultures of the Hindu and the Buddhist have become just shrubs, and the dividing force has become as great and as strong as oak".

The wealthiest country like Bharata is not like as it is now. Many foreign travelers and medieval historians wrote that they did not have enough words to describe the immense wealth and grandeur of Indian cities and temples. The splendid creativity, the scientific knowledge and the art of the Indians left the middle eastern and European travelers awestruck with admiration. Seeing India's boundless natural resources and the immense possibilities of its trade, European colonizers coveted her dazzling riches. Some 18th century accounts[2] say that the Europeans were disillusioned by the uninspiring life of Europe. When they saw Bharata's enchanting richness, it became their hunting ground. Portuguese, Dutch, French and British colonizer robbed the most beautiful creation and wealth of the world's greatest civilization. When they left they had ruined that Bharata, which they called India, which had once traded with Greeks, Romans and the Arabs. Overlooking What United India's culture, despite differences in religion, they divided Punjab and Bengal on religious lines. Tens of millions perished before India's partition. Million more died during partition and an Islamic state was carved out of India's soil. As Narendra Singh Sarila said[3]: many of the roots of Islamic terrorism sweeping the world today lie buried in the partition of India.

The Europeans believing in the supremacy of their religion and race blundered the world and destroyed the legacy of many cultures. They destroyed the cultural identities of native people, mocked traditional system of knowledge and exploited their economic wealth, often causing complete destitution. Africa was divided on the table arbitrarily. Today these divided culture are still bleeding. Native Americans were brutally exterminated by bullets, killed by blankets infected with infectious diseases, their land was captured breaking hundreds of treaties. Australia was overrun by killing the natives, but many western scholars spend their lives proclaiming that their race is the only predictor of justice, truth and human rights in the world. That they are the illuminators of civilizations on earth, that they are the progenitors of the countries, that they alone gave democracy to India, that their Aryan ancestor brought Sanskrit and Vedas into India, that the Greeks taught maths and philosophy to the world.

New excavations are pushing back the dates of Indian civilization further back. While western scholars are trying to prove that they are of much later period. This is done to help them to prove that most achievements of ancient India is actually originated in the west (example: Baudhayana theorem of 800 BCE is adopted from Pythagoras theorem of 540 BCE). The main reason for manipulating chronology is the motive to manipulate the cause of the things. So to show foreign cause of Indian thing, one should have the chronology. So all the manipulation of chronology is not innocent or being done just as a matter of accidental, there is always a political motive in manipulating chronology. The chronology of events is very important in understanding a civilization, because the chronology goes cause to effect. Cause always comes before the effect, we cannot have a cause with an effect before it. So for instance, if Abrahamic people wanted to show that their idea of origin of time and the beginning of Moses onwards, they want to fit whole world into that, because they want to show that theirs is the origin of all mankind and all influence came from there. So they force others to fit into their chronology. So when they discovered India, they had not understood there's so much knowledge here, they wanted to fit it into their framework and therefore they had to improvise when the Aryans must have come, to fit into their chronology. When the epics were written, as Mahabharata could not be older than their text. Because it would destroy their entire claim. Their tendency of calling the facts of Indian history a myth and describing ancient Indian philosophies as primitive speculations is growing bigger. This is distorting the history and culture of Indian Civilization. Myth is very dangerous term to use, because it says that it

didn't even happen, and you just made it up. So that invalidates the whole authenticity of a civilization. We should consider Itihaas as non-translatable and not as myth. The physical evidences were destroyed by invaders and center of learnings, where this itihaas is kept alive, were destroyed, so it become very easy for them to declare it as myth. But it is very important for us to reject the myth and reclaim the truth of our tradition and *Sanskriti*.

Sanskriti is very commonly translated to English as 'Culture'. Culture is defined as the quality in a person or society that arises from a concern for what is regarded as excellent in arts, letters, manners, scholarly pursuits etc. While the word *Sanskriti* comes from the root '*kri*' which means 'to do or to make' and the prefix *Sam* is applied before it to convey a sense of embellishment. It means actions done for the holistic refinement and perfection of all the potentialities within a human being. The purpose of *sanskriti* is to make an overall improvement in a person by adding things which are lacking, removing the ones which are bad and augmenting the ones which are good. *Sanskriti* embraces all the aspects of an individual's life and not merely confined to fine arts or performing arts. *Sanskriti* is meant for all sections of people in the society to uplift their consciousness. *Sanskriti* is concerned with actions for improvement in not only the domain of matter but also the domain of spirit. It is not a static concept like culture. *Sanskriti* is linked with the divine and higher purpose. True to the Vedic idea of reincarnation, *Sanskriti* is the not just concerned with one life span of an individual. *Sanskriti* is a prescriptive concept as it prescribes a way. Culture denotes a purely descriptive concept as it describes patterns of behaviour.

There are three ways of human behaviour in Indian tradition:

Prakriti: this is used in the sense of raw natural life without any refinement like the way animals lead their lives. Even a newly born person leads a *Prakritika* life for some time till his intellectual faculties develop.

Vikriti: This is degradation and deviation from the acceptable and beneficial norms of conduct by an individual or a group of individuals (e.g. drug addiction). It is acquired if a person is not regulated and providing proper guidance.

Sanskriti: This brings about an improvement in the faculties an individual and uplifts his consciousness.

So there is a culture in the west, but the land of Bharata has *Sanskriti*, which was destroyed by so called westernisation. According to M.N. Srinivas,[4]

"Westernisation" refers to "the changes brought about in the Indian society and culture as a result of over 150 years of British rule and the term subsumes changes occurring at different levels – technology, institutions, ideology and values." It seems that the aim of Macaulay Minute[5] was succeeded in his mission to create Indians in blood and color but English in taste and preference. Even nowadays Indians also start believing the way Macaulay wrote in his minute that "A single shelf of a good European library was worth the whole native literature of India and Arabia." That's why most of the time we study western scholars and historical writings and try to learn our *Shashtras* through western theories and perspectives. Even the way I am writing this research is somewhere is also in the western framework. The colonial rule of two centuries left a dark speck on our *Sanskriti*. Our socialization and academics forced us to fall in line with the conventional way of life dictated by the belief system of the western society.

Although we are greatly under the influence of western culture and the glory of our *Sanskriti* is faded out, but still something is there which attracts the people throughout the world to visit our nation, read out our *Shastras* and *Granthas* and accept the norms and values of our tradition. After realizing that Indian tradition is more scientific than the western society, some of them start living and loving India for their remaining life. The idea that India is considered as the most unsafe place for India[6] even does not feared them and a large population of foreigner women start loving our land and its tradition.

Women in Indian tradition is considered as 'Devi', the female goddesses, venerated in the land of Bharata as the source of Primordial power, the symbol of piety and purity. The *Devi Sukta* of Rig Veda, declares a feminine energy as the essence of universe, the one who creates all matter and consciousness, the eternal and infinite, the metaphysical and empirical reality (Brahman), the soul (supreme self) of everything. But with the passage of time, owing to socio-political turmoil and the gradual blurring of right ideology, resulting in degeneration of values, women began to lose their due place and were relegated to a lower position.

Main Text**The Appeal of Bharatiya Sanskriti to Western Women**

Bharatiya Sanskriti's profound spiritual teachings and holistic approach to life have long attracted Western women. This cultural allure is rooted in the deep spiritual significance of Bharata as a land of divine energy and consciousness. The ancient traditions of yoga, meditation, and the veneration of the feminine divine offer Western women an alternative to the often materialistic and individualistic values of their own cultures.

1. The Feminine Divine and Spiritual Empowerment

In Bharatiya Sanskriti, the concept of the feminine divine is central. Goddesses like Saraswati, Lakshmi, and Durga are venerated as symbols of knowledge, prosperity, and power. The Devi Sukta of the Rig Veda declares feminine energy as the essence of the universe, embodying both creation and consciousness. For Western women, disillusioned by patriarchal structures in their own societies, the worship of the feminine divine in India offers a source of empowerment and spiritual fulfillment. This reverence for the feminine draws many Western women to embrace and celebrate their own feminine power, finding in Bharatiya Sanskriti a spiritual path that honors their inherent worth and divinity.

2. The Journey to Bharatavarsha The journey of Western women to Bharatavarsha is not merely physical but also deeply spiritual. Drawn by the promise of spiritual wisdom and self-realization, these women seek out the teachings of Indian sages, the serenity of ashrams, and the transformative practices of yoga and meditation. Their experiences in India often lead to profound personal transformations, as they immerse themselves in the cultural and spiritual heritage of the land.

The Transformative Impact on Personal Lives

The adoption of Bharatiya Sanskriti has led to significant transformations in the personal lives of many Western women. This transformation is not only spiritual but also cultural, as these women begin to redefine their values and lifestyle choices.

1. Embracing Simplicity and Sustainability Bharatiya Sanskriti emphasizes living in harmony with nature and adopting a simple, sustainable lifestyle. Practices like Ahimsa (non-violence) and the reverence for natural resources resonate deeply with Western women, prompting them to adopt vegetarianism, reduce material consumption, and prioritize sustainable living practices. This shift towards simplicity aligns with their spiritual beliefs and contributes to a greater sense of peace and well-being.

2. Redefining Success and Happiness Influenced by the concept of Ananda (bliss) in Indian philosophy, Western women who embrace Bharatiya Sanskriti often shift their focus from external achievements to inner contentment. This redefinition of success and happiness, rooted in spiritual growth rather than material gain, leads to a more balanced and fulfilling life.

The Broader Cultural Exchange

The impact of Bharatiya Sanskriti on Western women extends beyond personal transformation; it also contributes to a broader cultural exchange between East and West. This exchange fosters a global dialogue on spirituality, well-being, and the pursuit of a meaningful life.

1. Challenging Western Supremacy and Stereotypes The experiences of Western women with Bharatiya Sanskriti challenge the stereotypes and misconceptions often associated with India. Historically, Western scholars and colonizers have attempted to undermine the achievements of Indian civilization, distorting its history and culture. The colonial narrative often portrayed India as a land of poverty and mysticism, while ignoring its rich spiritual and intellectual traditions. By embracing and sharing their experiences with Bharatiya Sanskriti, Western women help to dispel these misconceptions and promote a more nuanced understanding of Indian culture.

2. Reclaiming the Truth of Indian Civilization: As Western women immerse themselves in the study of Indian philosophy, they also become aware of the historical distortions and cultural erasure imposed by colonial powers. The systematic manipulation of chronology and the dismissal of ancient Indian achievements as myths are part of a broader attempt to undermine India's cultural identity. However, the growing interest in Bharatiya Sanskriti among Western women represents a reclamation of this cultural heritage. By rejecting the

narrative of Western supremacy and embracing the spiritual wisdom of Bharata, these women contribute to the preservation and revitalization of India's ancient traditions.

3. Promoting Global Spirituality: The influence of Bharatiya Sanskriti on Western women also promotes a more inclusive and diverse understanding of spirituality on a global scale. By sharing their experiences and insights, these women encourage others to explore different spiritual traditions and question their own beliefs. This global dialogue fosters a deeper appreciation of the interconnectedness of all spiritual paths and contributes to a more spiritually aware global community.

The Impact of Ancient Bharatiya Sanskriti on Western Women

In this context, the impact of Ancient Bharatiya Sanskriti on Western women presents an intriguing facet of cultural exchange and transformation. Despite the degradation of traditional values under Westernization, the allure of Bharatiya Sanskriti has captivated many Westerners, particularly women, who have sought to embrace its profound spiritual and cultural heritage.

Attraction to Indian Spirituality

Western women have been drawn to the spiritual aspects of Bharatiya Sanskriti, particularly its philosophical and meditative practices. The concept of Shakti, representing feminine divine energy, resonates deeply with many Western women who find empowerment and inspiration in the portrayal of women as embodiments of divine power and wisdom. Texts such as the Devi Sukta from the Rig Veda articulate a vision of feminine energy as the essence of the universe, creating matter and consciousness, and embodying the eternal and infinite.

The allure of Indian spirituality often translates into Western women engaging in practices such as yoga, meditation, and Ayurvedic healing. These practices, rooted in ancient Indian traditions, offer an alternative to the materialism and stress prevalent in Western societies. Many Western women find these practices provide not only physical well-being but also a profound sense of spiritual connection and inner peace.

Embracing Indian Philosophy and Lifestyle

Beyond spirituality, Western women have been increasingly interested in Indian philosophical traditions. The teachings of Vedanta, which emphasize the unity of all existence and the pursuit of self-realization, offer a contrast to the individualistic and competitive nature of Western cultures. This philosophical approach encourages a holistic view of life that integrates material and spiritual dimensions, appealing to those seeking a more balanced and meaningful existence.

The principles of Ayurveda, an ancient Indian system of medicine, also attract Western women looking for natural and personalized approaches to health. Ayurveda's emphasis on balance and harmony within the body aligns with a growing trend in the West towards holistic and integrative health practices.

Cultural Integration and Personal Transformation

Western women who immerse themselves in Bharatiya Sanskriti often experience significant personal transformation. The values of non-violence (ahimsa), compassion, and simplicity, central to Indian traditions, can inspire a shift in lifestyle and priorities. Many Western women find that adopting these values fosters a greater sense of contentment and purpose in their lives.

The practice of embracing Indian cultural elements, such as traditional dress (sarees) and rituals, also reflects a deep appreciation for Bharatiya Sanskriti. By integrating these elements into their lives, Western women honor and celebrate the rich cultural heritage of Bharata, contributing to a broader cultural exchange.

Challenges and Misconceptions

However, the integration of Bharatiya Sanskriti into Western lives is not without challenges. Misinterpretations and superficial engagements can sometimes lead to the commodification of Indian traditions, where practices are adopted without a genuine

understanding of their cultural and philosophical contexts. This can result in a dilution of the traditions and a misunderstanding of their significance.

Additionally, the complexities of cultural appropriation must be navigated carefully. Western women who adopt Indian practices must be mindful of respecting the traditions and acknowledging their origins, rather than merely appropriating them for personal gain.

Conclusion

The sacred land of Bharata, with its deep spiritual and cultural heritage, has had a profound impact on Western women who seek to understand and integrate its traditions into their lives. Despite the challenges and historical upheavals that have marred its legacy, the enduring appeal of Bharatiya Sanskriti lies in its holistic and spiritually enriching aspects. The interplay between ancient Indian wisdom and contemporary Western values offers a unique opportunity for cross-cultural dialogue and personal growth.

As Western women embrace the teachings and practices of Bharatiya Sanskriti, they contribute to a renewed appreciation of its ancient wisdom and its relevance in the modern world. This cultural exchange fosters a deeper understanding and respect for the rich heritage of Bharata, bridging gaps between diverse traditions and promoting a more inclusive global dialogue.

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Endnote

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